

The Influence of Public Services on Employee Performance at The BPKPAD Office, Binjai City

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Abstract

The aim of this research is to determine and analyze the influence of Public Services on Performance at the Binjai City BPKPAD Office. This research was carried out at the BPKPAD Office in Binjai City. The type of research is associative quantitative. The population in this study was 190 employees with ASN and honorary status in the General Section of the Binjai City BPKPAD Office. The sampling technique in this study used the Slovin technique, which consisted of 129 people. The research results show that Public Services have a significant influence on Performance as shown by the T-Statistic value of $5.664 > 1.656$ and the P Value of $0.000 < 0.05$. The adjusted R Square value is 0.195 or 19.50%, which means that public services have a low influence on employee performance, while the remaining 80.50% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied. This shows that improvements in Public Services can improve Performance at the Binjai City BPKPAD Office.

Keywords: public service; employee performance

INTRODUCTION

The government is an institution whose operational principle is to serve the community (public servant) in various aspects of social life. Meanwhile, a government agency is an organization or institution (container) that focuses on services to the community. The government's role is important because there is no other institution that is willing and able to carry out social functions without the hope of getting private benefits. This is natural and in accordance with the principles of economic democracy, where the government's function is apart from being an innovator (starting) but also as a motivator (encouraging) and even a facilitator (facilitating public services both physically and administratively in the bureaucracy).

On the other hand, one source of regional income to finance development is taxes, where the government as an innovator (who initiates) as well as a motivator (who encourages) and even a facilitator (who facilitates public services), is very challenged to increase public awareness in paying taxes. There are many ways the government can increase people's motivation to pay taxes. One of them is linking behind the name, which is a collaboration with other government agencies. This means that if a person wants to change their name, it is stipulated that the person must pay the tax in the current month, after that they will apply for a change of name.

Therefore, to be able to improve the quality of service for employees, the government must provide work motivation for employees. If employees feel that their work motivation is high enough, then their performance can be improved. This means that the quality of service provided by employees is very dependent on their job satisfaction

and work motivation which ultimately results in increased performance. Indeed, high work motivation usually comes from within the employee, but it all depends on the person.

From the results of interviews conducted with different public sector employees, there are 3 things that have the most influence on job satisfaction, namely job level, leadership and co-workers. In both public and private sector organizations, job satisfaction is interconnected with motivation (Hasby, 2020). Motivation is the encouragement and enthusiasm of employees to increase their self-confidence so that they are enthusiastic about carrying out their work. According to (Asy et al., 2021) job satisfaction is correlated with public service motivation. Public service motivation is the tendency of a person or individual to respond uniquely to motives within the scope of public sector organizations (Perry & Wise, 1990).

Based on Law Number 25 of 2009 article one (1) concerning Public Services provides the following definition of public services: "Public Services are activities or a series of activities in order to fulfill service needs in accordance with statutory regulations for every citizen and resident for goods, services, and/or administrative services provided by public service providers".

Public Service is the provision of services (serving) the needs of people or society who have an interest in the organization in accordance with the basic rules and procedures that have been established, (Mukarom & Laksana, 2016). In order to obtain this satisfaction, indicators of quality public services, such as:

- 1) Openness. It is appropriate that services are transparent and easy to access or obtain.
- 2) Accountability. Service responsibilities are based on law.
- 3) Conditional, namely services based on the conditions or abilities of the party providing or receiving services that refer to the principle of effectiveness.
- 4) Involvement, namely services that direct community participation while providing public services by taking into account the needs, aspirations and desires of users.
- 5) Balanced rights, namely services that are fair and do not appear to be discriminatory.
- 6) Rights are balanced and mandatory. Services that consider fairness between givers and recipients of public services. (Mukarom & Laksana, 2016)

According to (Fahmi, 2017) Performance is the result of a process that is referred to and measured over a certain period of time based on previously established provisions or agreements. Meanwhile, according to (Mangkunegara, 2016) employee performance is the achievement of employee work results based on quality and quantity as work performance within a certain period of time which is adjusted to the duties and responsibilities of a group within the organization in carrying out main tasks and functions that are guided by norms, standard operating procedures. , criteria and measures that have been established or are applicable in the organization.

To measure the level of employee performance in this research the author refers to theory (Fahmi, 2017), namely:

- 1) Quality, namely the level of errors, damage, accuracy.
- 2) Quantity, namely the number of jobs produced.

- 3) Use of time at work, namely the level of absenteeism, tardiness, effective working time/lost working hours.
- 4) Cooperate with other people at work.

The purpose of this research is to analyze and determine the influence of Public Services on Employee Performance of the Binjai City BPKPAD Office. The concept of this research is as depicted in the following conceptual framework image:

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

METHOD

This type of research is casual associative quantitative research. This research was carried out at the Office of the Regional Financial Revenue and Asset Management Agency (BPKPAD) in Binjai City. This research was carried out from May 2024 to June 2024. According to (Sugiyono, 2018b) population is a generalized area consisting of objects/subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics determined by the researcher to be studied and then conclusions drawn. The population in this study were all employees of the North Sumatra Regional Disaster Management Agency (BPD), totaling 186 people with the following details:

Table 1. Total Population

Status	Amount
Civil servants	90
Honorary/Task Force	100
Total	190

In formulating the research sample, the Slovin formula was used as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Information:

n = Sample size/number of respondents

N = Population size

e = Percentage of allowance for sampling accuracy that is still possible tolerated;

e = 0.1

In the Slovin formula there are the following provisions:

The value of e = 0.1 (10%) for large populations

The value of e = 0.2 (20%) for small populations

So the sample range that can be taken from the Solvin technique is between 10-20% of the research population. The total population in this study was 186 employees, so the

percentage of allowance used was 10% and the calculation results could be rounded to achieve suitability. So to find out the research sample, use the following calculations:

$$\begin{aligned}n &= \frac{190}{1 + \frac{190(0,05)^2}{190}} \\n &= \frac{190}{1 + 190(0,0025)} \\n &= \frac{190}{1 + 0,465} \\n &= \frac{190}{1,465} \\n &= 128,81 = 129\end{aligned}$$

Based on the calculations above, the sample of respondents in this study was adjusted to 129 people or around 67.89% of all employees at the Binjai City BPKPAD Office. This was done to make data processing easier and for better test results. The samples taken were based on probability sampling techniques; simple random sampling, where the researcher provides an equal opportunity for each member of the population to be selected as a random sample without paying attention to the strata in the population itself. The following are details of the number of samples taken:

Table 2. Number of Samples

Status	Total Population	Sample Percentage	Number of Samples
Civil servants	90	67.89% x 90 = 61.01	61
Honorary/task force	100	67.89% x 100 = 67.89	68
Total	186		129

The data that will be used from this research is the data from the questionnaire distributed to respondents consisting of all employees in all divisions. The data analysis technique used in this research is a quantitative data analysis method using SPSS version 25.0.

Validity and reliability tests were carried out in order to test the quality of the research data. The validity test decision making criteria are as follows: If $r_{count} > r_{table}$, then the question item is valid. If $r_{count} < r_{table}$, then the question item is invalid. Meanwhile, the reliability test criteria are formulated if $r_{alpha} > r_{table}$ then the statement is reliable and if $r_{alpha} < r_{table}$ then the statement is not reliable.

The linear regression model was formulated in this research with the following formula:

$$Y = a + bX$$

Where :

Y = Employee Performance

X = Public Service

a = Constant

b = Regression coefficient

The t-test in this research was carried out to determine the significance of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable,(Kuncoro & Hardani, 2013). According to(Kuncoro & Hardani, 2013)The determination test (R^2) is used to measure how much influence the independent variable has on the dependent variable. In other words, the coefficient of determination is used to assess the magnitude of the influence of the independent variable studied, namely Public Services (X), on the dependent variable, namely employee performance (Y). The coefficient of determination (R^2) value ranges from zero to one ($0 < R^2 < 1$) which means, if $R^2 = 0$, then there is no influence between variable (X) and variable (Y). Conversely, if R^2 approaches 1, then the influence between variable (X) and variable (Y) becomes stronger. Testing of the coefficient of determination was carried out using SPSS version 25.0 software.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Contents Results and Discussion

1. Research result

a) Descriptive Analysis

Descriptive Analysis This test is used to determine the minimum and maximum scores, the highest score, the rating score and the standard deviation of each variable. The results are as follows:

Table 3. Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Public service	129	1.50	5.00	4.0608	,72660
Performance	129	2.00	5.00	4.1764	,74504
Valid N (listwise)	129				

The table above shows that the measurement results show that respondents assess Public Services and employee performance at the Binjai City Regional Revenue and Asset Financial Management Agency (BPKPAD) Office as above average, with mean values of 4,060 and 4,176 respectively on a scale of 1- 5. The variation in respondents' assessments of these two variables is quite moderate, with almost the same standard deviation (0.726 for Public Services and 0.745 for employee performance), indicating that although there are individual differences in perceptions, the majority of respondents have quite positive views of these two variables.

b) Validity and Reliability Test Results

Validity Test Results

The validity test is used to measure whether a questionnaire is valid or not. Validity testing carried out in this research was through the Corrected Item-Total Correlation test or better known as Person Correlation.

Table 4. Validity Test Results for Public Service Variables (X)

Variable	Correlation Value	Probability	Information
PP1	0.605 > 0.172	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
PP2	0.691 > 0.172	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
PP3	0.645 > 0.172	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
PP4	0.770 > 0.172	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
PP5	0.596 > 0.172	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
PP6	0.640 > 0.172	0.000 < 0.05	Valid

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25

From the data above, it can be stated that the indicators for the Public Service variable have a correlation coefficient value of > 0.172 with a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$, so it can be concluded that the indicators for the Public Service variable are valid, (Sugiyono, 2018a).

Table 5. Validity Test Results for Employee Performance Variables (Y)

Variable	Correlation Value	Probability	Information
KIN1	0.770 > 0.172	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
KIN2	0.732 > 0.172	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
KIN3	0.693 > 0.172	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
KIN4	0.732 > 0.172	0.000 < 0.05	Valid

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25

From the data above, it can be stated that all indicators on the employee performance variable have a correlation coefficient value greater than 0.172 with a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$, so it can be concluded that the statements for the employee performance variable are valid, (Sugiyono, 2018a).

Reliability Test Results

According to (Ghozali, 2018) the reliability test aims to measure how reliable or reliable the questionnaire distributed to respondents is, which is useful as an instrument in this research. The reliability measurement method used in this research is by looking at the Cronbach Alpha (α) value. The questionnaire is declared reliable if the Cronbach Alpha (α) value is > 0.61 .

Table 6. Reliability Test Results

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
Public service	0.734	6
Employee Performance	0.711	4

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25.0

Based on table 5, it is known that the Cronbach Alpha (α) value of the Public Service and employee performance variables is greater than 0.60. So it can be concluded that all

indicators in the variable instrument are declared reliable or reliable so that they can proceed to research hypothesis testing

c) Quantitative Analysis

This analysis is intended to determine the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable. The test results are as follows:

Simple Linear Regression Analysis

This regression test is intended to determine changes in the dependent variable if the independent variable experiences changes. The test results are as follows:

Table 7. Simple Linear Regression Test Results

Model	Unstandardized		Standardized	t	Sig.
	Coefficients		Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	2,307	,335		6,878	,000
Public service	,460	,081	,449	5,664	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Performance

Based on the test results in table 8, the regression equation $Y = 2.307 + 0.460X$ is obtained. This equation is explained as follows: 1) A constant of 2.307 means that if there is no public service, then there is an employee performance of 2.307 points. The Public Service regression coefficient is 0.460, meaning that Public Service influences an increase in employee performance of 0.460 for every 1 point increase.

Analysis of the Coefficient of Determination

To determine the magnitude of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable, a coefficient of determination analysis was carried out. The test results are as follows:

Table 8. Coefficient of Determination Test Results

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,449a	,202	,195	,66830

a. Predictors: (Constant), Public Services

The test results in table 7 show an Adjusted R Square value of 0.195 or 19.50%, which means that Public Services have a low influence on employee performance while the remaining 80.50% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied.

t Test Results (Hypothesis Test)

Hypothesis testing with the t test is used to determine whether or not there is an influence of the dependent variable on the independent variable with the following hypothesis formulation:

Ho: There is no influence of Public Services on employee performance at the Binjai City Regional Revenue and Asset Financial Management Agency (BPKPAD) Office

Ha: There is an influence of Public Services on employee performance at the Binjai City Regional Revenue and Asset Financial Management Agency (BPKPAD) Office

The following are the results of the hypothesis test as shown in the following table:

Table 9. Hypothesis Test Results

Model	Unstandardized		Standardized	t	Sig.
	Coefficients		Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	2,307	,335		6,878	,000
Public service	,460	,081	,449	5,664	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Performance

Based on the test results in table 8, the calculated t value is $5.664 > t$ table 1.656, with a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$, thus it can be stated that Ho is rejected and Ha is accepted or that there is a positive and significant influence between Public Services on employee performance at the Management Agency Office. Binjai City Regional Income and Asset Finance (BPKPAD).

Contents of Discussion Results

The findings in this research can be strengthened by referring to relevant previous research findings. In the context of the influence of Public Services on Performance, the results of this research are in accordance with previous research conducted by (Saragih et al., 2023) conducting research entitled The Influence of Public Services on the Performance of Samarinda City Cleaning and Parks Service Employees which shows that public services have a positive and positive effect. significant impact on the performance of Samarinda City Cleaning and Parks Department employees. This means that improvements in Public Services contribute which will have an impact on improving Performance.

CLOSING

Conclusion

From the results of data analysis resulting from the research and discussion described above, it can be concluded that Public Services (interpersonal relationships) have a significant influence on Performance at the Binjai City BPKPAD Office with a calculated t value of $5.664 > t$ table 1.656, with a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$ These results

indicate that if services to the public are improved, performance tends to increase. The results of this research provide practical implications for management and improvement in the work environment to increase performance through attention to these factors.

The adjusted R Square value is 0.195 or 19.50%, which means that public services have a low influence on employee performance, while the remaining 80.50% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied.

Suggestions and Acknowledgments

Based on the results of the research, discussion and conclusions obtained, suggestions that can be given are that the Public Service variable needs to be maintained and improved. Therefore, the leadership of the Binjai City BPKPAD Office should increase motivation for employees. The motivation given must also be more diverse, both verbal and nonverbal, because with diverse motivation it is hoped that employee performance will be improved. It is hoped that these steps can further increase employee motivation, thereby improving public services and also improving employee performance.

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